

EMBRACING THE FUTURE: EXPLORING TEACHERS PERSPECTIVE AND READINESS FOR INTEGRATING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN MATHEMATICS CLASSROOM IN SELECTED PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the readiness and perspective of senior high school mathematics teachers in integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in their classrooms. It aimed to examine the relationship between teacher demographics, AI familiarity, perspectives, and readiness for AI adoption, identify challenges and barriers, explore potential benefits, and propose interventions. A descriptive-correlational design was employed, involving 37 senior high school mathematics teachers from Quezon City and Marinduque. Data was collected through a survey questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results showed a somewhat moderate familiarity with AI tools, a high perceived ease of use, usefulness, and perceived challenges, and a high level of teacher readiness. A negative correlation between familiarity and readiness was observed, potentially due to the familiarity breeds caution effect. Conversely, a positive correlation existed between perspective and readiness, indicating that favorable views on AI's ease of use, usefulness, and manageable challenges increased readiness for adoption. Key challenges identified included a need for more AI familiarity, lack of resources, and professional training on AI integration.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Mathematics Education, Teacher Readiness, Teacher Perspective, AI Familiarity*

INTRODUCTION

Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into math education aligns with the goals of Education 5.0 by enabling personalized and adaptive learning experiences. AI tools like intelligent tutors, math problem solvers, online graphing calculators, and chatbots have immense potential to transform math achievement, motivation, and confidence through customized support and instant feedback (Ayanwale et al., 2022; Melo, 2023). However, challenges exist, including limited technical capacity of AI systems, teachers' AI-specific technological and pedagogical knowledge gaps, and the need for context-specific AI tools (Seo et al., 2021; Melo, 2023; Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Teaching and Learning, 2023).

One of the most observed challenges in integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into education is the limited technical capacity of AI systems. This limitation can impact the effectiveness and usability of AI tools in the classroom. Teachers' AI-specific technological and pedagogical knowledge, the current limitations of AI systems, and the need for context-specific AI tools all contribute to this challenge (Seo et al., 2021). To effectively integrate AI into education, teachers must have a solid understanding of AI and its applications in the classroom (Melo, 2023). However, many teachers still need to gain the technological skills for efficient digital learning or implementing AI in the classroom (Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Teaching and Learning, 2023). This knowledge gap can hinder the successful implementation of AI tools and limit their potential impact on teaching and learning.

To support teachers in developing AI readiness, various frameworks and training programs have been proposed, focusing on empowering educators to utilize AI effectively in their teaching practice (Luckin et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Koehler, 2023). UNESCO also recognized AI's potential to address pressing educational concerns and revolutionize teaching and learning techniques (Artificial Intelligence in Education, 2023).

This study aims to uncover teacher perspectives and readiness to integrate AI in the mathematics classroom of selected public and private senior high schools. Teachers' perspectives, experiences, and expectations must be considered for successful AI implementation (Chan, 2023; Wang et al., 2023; Celik et al., 2022). The study aligns with the concept of Education 5.0, which emphasizes integrating advanced technologies, including AI, to enhance the learning experience and foster 21st-century skills (Kim & Kim, 2022).

While AI offers promising benefits for math education, careful implementation addressing context-specific challenges is needed. Multiple studies highlight AI's potential to address math achievement, motivation, and confidence challenges through personalized support and feedback (Kim & Kim, 2022; Melo, 2023; Ayanwale et al., 2022; Artificial Intelligence in Education, 2023). However, realizing the full potential requires ongoing research, development, and frameworks focused on improving teachers' AI readiness (Luckin et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Celik et al., 2022; Chan, 2023).

The study aims to provide data-driven insights into the advantages AI offers educators versus the realities they face regarding technological and pedagogical knowledge. The researcher proposed an intervention program to empower teachers to effectively leverage AI in enhancing math education aligned with the vision for personalized learning in Education 5.0 models.

Research Questions

These research questions aimed to explore teacher perspectives, uncover their concerns and expectations, assess their perceptions of benefits and challenges, examine the factors influencing readiness, and identify potential implications for effectively supporting teachers in integrating artificial intelligence.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Sex
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 Educational Qualification
 - 1.4 Length of Service
 - 1.5 Technological Competence
 - 1.6 AI tools commonly used in teaching mathematics
2. How familiar are the teachers with various AI tools in teaching Mathematics courses?
 - 2.1 Familiarity with AI tools
 - 2.2 Familiarity with the common features of AI
 - 2.3 Familiarity with integrating AI into teaching
3. What is the teacher's perspective on using AI tools in teaching Mathematics in terms of:
 - 3.1 ease of use
 - 3.2 usefulness
 - 3.3 perceive challenges of AI integration
4. What is the level of readiness of mathematics teachers in using various AI tools in instruction?
5. Is there a significant relationship between respondents:
 - 5.1 profile and level of familiarity
 - 5.2 profile and teachers' perspective
 - 5.3 profile and level of readiness
 - 5.4 level of familiarity and readiness
 - 5.5 teachers' perspective and readiness
6. What intervention program can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the relationships between familiarity, perspective and readiness of Senior High School Teacher for integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Mathematics Classroom. Conducted in Fairview Quezon City and Marinduque, the study sampled 37 Senior High School teachers from two (2) public and two (2) private Senior High School using Purposive sampling (Total Sampling). Data were gathered through Survey questionnaires develop by the researcher. Validity war ensured through expert feedback, leading to enhancements in questionnaires. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson R and Spearman Rank Correlation to assess relationship and differences among variables.

RESULTS

I. Demographic Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

Table 1 to 3 below present the demographic profile regarding sex, age, educational qualification, length of service, technological competencies, and familiarity with AI tools commonly used in teaching mathematics.

Table 1.

Demographic Profile of Senior High School Mathematics Teachers in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

	Profile	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	23	62.2
	Female	14	37.8
	Total	100	100.0
Age	21 – 25	6	16.2
	26 – 30	12	32.5
	31 – 35	6	16.2
	36 – 40	7	18.9
	41 – 45	2	5.4
	46 – 50	2	5.4
	51 – 55	1	2.7
	56 – 60	1	2.7
	Total	100	100.0
Educational Qualification	Bachelor's Degree	16	43.3
	With earned units in a Master's Degree	15	40.5
	Master's Degree	3	8.1
	With earned units in Doctoral Degree	3	8.1
	Total	100	100.0
Length of Service	Below 6 years	14	37.8
	6 to 10 years	15	40.6
	Above 10 years	8	21.6
	Total	100	100.0

Table 2

Technical Competence of Senior High School Mathematics Teachers in Selected Public and Private Secondary Schools

Indicators		Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
1.	I stay up-to-date on new technological developments and tools.	4.14	0.71	A	4.5
2.	I have sufficient knowledge of technologies to use them effectively in my work/teaching.	4.08	0.55	A	6.5
3.	I feel confident in my ability to learn new technologies quickly.	4.51	0.73	SA	1
4.	I can troubleshoot basic technical problems when they arise.	3.89	0.70	A	13
5.	I know how to find solutions when I encounter a technical problem such as (seeking help, researching, or using available resources).	4.14	0.82	A	4.5
6.	I am skilled at using computers, software programs, and new apps which are used in teaching mathematics.	3.97	0.76	A	9.5
7.	I can adapt technologies for different purposes as needed.	4.27	0.73	SA	2.5
8.	I am comfortable using digital collaboration tools (e.g. video conferencing, shared docs).	4.27	0.73	SA	2.5
9.	I can effectively integrate new technologies into my work processes and routines.	4.05	0.74	A	8
10.	I can help my less tech-savvy peers troubleshoot problems with their devices or software.	3.70	1.00	A	16
11.	I know how to optimize, customize, and modify settings on platforms or devices to suit my needs.	3.92	0.72	A	12
12.	I believe I have the technology skills needed to thrive in a modern workplace/classroom.	4.08	0.68	A	6.5
13.	I frequently learn about new technologies on my initiative to improve my skills.	3.97	0.80	A	9.5
14.	I know how to assess the credibility and functionality of a new tool or platform.	3.95	0.81	A	11
15.	I stay on top of digital security best practices for protecting my data and privacy.	3.86	0.79	A	14
16.	I can provide informed recommendations about technologies to others based on their specific needs and goals.	3.76	0.86	A	15
Grand Mean		4.04	0.76	A	

Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	The level of technological competence is very high
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	The level of technological competence is high
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	The level of technological competence is average
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	The level of technological competence is low
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	The level of technological competence is very low

Table 3

Artificial Intelligence Tools Commonly Used in Teaching Mathematics in Selected Public and Private Secondary Schools

AI Tools		Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
Step-by-Step Math Problem Solvers	1. Photomath	2.62	1.21	S	2
	2. Mathway	2.76	1.32	S	1
	3. Gauhmath	2.16	1.12	R	4.5
	4. Symbolab	2.16	1.19	R	4.5
	5. Microsoft Math Solver	2.30	1.13	R	3
	6. Question.AI – AI Math Solver	2.00	0.88	R	6
Composite Mean		2.33	1.14	R	
	1. ChatGPT	2.65	1.36	S	1

Math Assistants/ Tutors	2. Mathbot – Math chatbot	1.86	1.11	R	3
	3. Wolfram Alpha	2.08	1.19	R	2
	Composite Mean	2.20	1.22	R	
Graphing/ Geometry Tools	1. Desmos	3.08	1.46	S	1
	2. Geogebra	2.97	1.46	S	2
	3. Graphmatica	1.95	1.13	R	3
	Composite Mean	2.67	1.35	S	
Computer Algebra Systems	1. Maple	1.78	1.03	N	2
	2. Mathematica	1.95	1.05	R	1
	Composite Mean	1.86	1.04	R	
Programming Computation Tools	1. MATLAB	2.03	1.30	R	1
	2. Octave	1.78	1.11	N	2
	Composite Mean	1.91	1.21	R	
Assessment Tools	1. Quizizz	3.43	1.42	O	1
	2. Kahoot	2.86	1.32	S	2
	3. Mentimeter	2.62	1.34	S	3
	4. Socrative	2.14	1.13	R	4
	Composite Mean	2.76	1.30	S	
Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation		
5	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Use daily		
4	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	Use 3-4 times a week		
3	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Use once a week		
2	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Use once a month		
1	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Do not use at all		

II. Familiarity of Teachers with Various AI tools

Table 4 to 6 illustrates the teachers' familiarity with AI tools, familiarity with common features of AI, and familiarity with integrating AI in teaching. These are the variables that are presumed to affect the perception and readiness of the respondents.

Table 4

Familiarity of Senior High School Mathematics Teacher to Various AI Tools in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

	AI tools	Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
Step-by-Step Math Problem Solvers	1. Photomath	3.43	1.42	MF	1
	2. Mathway	3.35	1.60	SOF	2
	3. Gauhmath	2.43	1.44	SLF	5
	4. Symbolab	2.54	1.52	SLF	3.5
	5. Microsoft Math Solver	2.54	1.45	SLF	3.5
	6. Question.AI – AI Math Solver	2.30	1.37	SLF	6
	Composite Mean	2.77	1.47	SOF	
Math Assistants/ Tutors	1. ChatGPT	3.92	1.30	MF	1
	2. Mathbot – Math chatbot	2.49	1.50	SLF	3
	3. Wolfram Alpha	2.59	1.52	SLF	2
	Composite Mean	3.00	1.44	SOF	
Graphing/ Geometry Tools	1. Desmos	3.49	1.50	MF	2
	2. Geogebra	3.57	1.48	MF	1
	3. Graphmatica	2.62	1.48	SOF	3
	Composite Mean	3.23	1.49	SOF	
Computer Algebra Systems	1. Maple	2.03	1.34	SLF	2
	2. Mathematica	2.16	1.38	SLF	1
	Composite Mean	2.09	1.36	SLF	

Programming Computation Tools	1. MATLAB	2.30	1.54	SLF	1
	2. Octave	2.00	1.35	SLF	2
	Composite Mean	2.15	1.45	SLF	
Assessment Tools	1. Quizizz	3.92	1.40	MF	1
	2. Kahoot	3.54	1.48	MF	2
	3. Mentimeter	3.22	1.70	SOF	3
	4. Socrative	2.49	1.54	SLF	4
	Composite Mean	3.29	1.53	SOF	
Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation		
5	4.21 – 5.00	Extremely Familiar (EF)	The level of familiarity is very high		
4	3.41 – 4.20	Moderately Familiar (MF)	The level of familiarity is high		
3	2.61 – 3.40	Somewhat Familiar (SOF)	The level of familiarity is average		
2	1.81 – 2.60	Slightly Familiar (SLF)	The level of familiarity is low		
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not at All Familiar (NF)	The level of familiarity is very low		

Table 5

Familiarity of Senior High School Mathematics Teacher with Common Features of AI Tools in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

	Common Features	Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
Step-by-step Math Problem Solvers	1. Give step-by-step solutions for a wide range of math problems.	3.70	1.24	MF	2
	2. Generates solutions with steps for common questions.	3.78	1.32	MF	1
	3. Shows work and explanations for each step.	3.62	1.28	MF	3
	Composite Mean	3.70	1.28	MF	
Math assistants/ Tutors	1. Can explain concepts conversationally like a human,	3.57	1.26	MF	2
	2. Answers questions and clarifies math ideas.	3.68	1.25	MF	1
	3. Provides deep explanations across math topics.	3.49	1.24	MF	3
	Composite Mean	3.58	1.25	MF	
Graphing/ Geometry Tools	1. Allows interactive graphs and geometry.	3.86	1.08	MF	1
	2. Let's you visualize and move math objects.	3.78	1.16	MF	2
	3. Includes tools to build and analyze shapes.	3.65	1.30	MF	3
	Composite Mean	3.77	1.18	MF	
Computer Algebra Systems	1. Has a powerful engine for symbolic math.	3.24	1.42	SOF	2
	2. Performs complex math analysis.	3.22	1.29	SOF	3
	3. Handles many kinds of equations.	3.27	1.33	SOF	1
	Composite Mean	3.24	1.35	SOF	
Programming Computation Tools	1. Optimized to do math programming.	3.19	1.35	SOF	2
	2. Enables hard science computations	3.11	1.35	SOF	3
	3. Comes with math functions built-in.	3.30	1.31	SOF	1
	Composite Mean	3.20	1.34	SOF	
Assessment Tools	1. Build quizzes, surveys, etc.	4.00	1.08	MF	1
	2. Collects and checks data.	3.97	1.04	MF	2
	3. Allows interactive question types.	3.95	1.00	MF	3

		Composite Mean	3.97	1.04	MF
Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation		
5	4.21 – 5.00	Extremely Familiar (EF)	The level of familiarity is very high		
4	3.41 – 4.20	Moderately Familiar (MF)	The level of familiarity is high		
3	2.61 – 3.40	Somewhat Familiar (SOF)	The level of familiarity is average		
2	1.81 – 2.60	Slightly Familiar (SLF)	The level of familiarity is low		
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not at All Familiar (NF)	The level of familiarity is very low		

Table 6

Familiarity of Senior High School Mathematics Teacher with Integration AI in Teaching in Selected Public and Private Secondary Schools

		Indicators	Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
1.	I understand how AI tutors provide personalized math instruction for students' needs.		3.51	1.24	MF	7.5
2.	I am familiar with AI math tools that respond and adapt to each student's skills and pace of learning.		3.49	1.19	MF	9
3.	I know how intelligent math software can automatically generate math practice problems.		3.59	1.21	MF	3
4.	I am aware of AI math helpers that give feedback, hints, and answers to students in real time while they work.		3.57	1.21	MF	4.5
5.	I understand how AI math tools assess student work and adjust their teaching methods accordingly.		3.54	1.19	MF	6
6.	I know AI software can create customized math tests, quizzes, and worksheets tailored to each student.		3.68	1.23	MF	1
7.	I have seen AI chatbots for math that let students ask questions by typing regular sentences.		3.51	1.22	MF	7.5
8.	I understand how AI looks at where students make mistakes to identify and improve areas where knowledge is missing.		3.41	1.17	SOF	10
9.	I know AI can recommend extra study materials and plans to students based on their progress in math.		3.57	1.12	MF	4.5
10.	I am familiar with AI tools that use data visuals and graphics to help demonstrate abstract math ideas.		3.65	1.30	MF	2
11.	I understand how AI uses simulated math experiments to build students' deeper understanding of concepts.		3.38	1.23	SOF	11
12.	I know AI can automatically flag students who are struggling in math for the teacher to help.		3.19	1.29	SOF	12
Grand Mean			3.51	1.22	MF	
Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation			
5	4.21 – 5.00	Extremely Familiar (EF)	The level of familiarity is very high			
4	3.41 – 4.20	Moderately Familiar (MF)	The level of familiarity is high			
3	2.61 – 3.40	Somewhat Familiar (SOF)	The level of familiarity is average			
2	1.81 – 2.60	Slightly Familiar (SLF)	The level of familiarity is low			
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not at All Familiar (NF)	The level of familiarity is very low			

III. Teachers Perspective in Using AI tools in teaching Mathematics

Table 7 to 9 shows the teachers perceived ease of use, usefulness, and challenges of AI integration. These are the variables that are presumed to affect the perception and readiness of the respondents.

Table 7

Perceived Ease of Use of Senior High School Mathematics Teachers on AI Tools in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

Indicators	Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
1. I find AI integration in my mathematics classroom to be user-friendly and easy to navigate.	3.73	0.87	A	8
2. I believe that using AI tools is straightforward and intuitive for both teachers and students.	3.89	0.91	A	3.5
3. I perceive AI applications as accessible and not overly complex.	3.76	0.89	A	7
4. I consider AI integration to be a hassle-free process in terms of implementation	3.70	0.97	A	9
5. I am convinced that using AI in teaching is a smooth and trouble-free experience.	3.86	0.89	A	5
6. I anticipate that AI integration will require minimal effort in terms of setup and management.	3.84	0.93	A	6
7. I see AI tools as a convenient addition to my teaching practices.	3.97	0.96	A	1.5
8. I expect that AI integration will be seamless and enhance the teaching experience.	3.89	0.99	A	3.5
9. I envision AI as a tool that simplifies tasks and reduces administrative burden.	3.97	0.87	A	1.5
Grand Mean	3.85	0.92	A	

Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	The level of perceived ease of use is very high
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	The level of perceived ease of use is high
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	The level of perceived ease of use is average
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	The level of perceived ease of use is low
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	The level of perceived ease of use is very low

Table 8

Perceived Usefulness of Senior High School Mathematics Teachers on AI Tools in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

Indicators	Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
1. I believe that AI integration will significantly enhance my teaching and students' learning.	4.00	0.85	A	4.5
2. I perceive AI as a valuable tool for improving educational outcomes in mathematics.	4.00	0.85	A	4.5
3. I view AI integration as a practical and effective approach to personalized learning.	4.03	0.80	A	2
4. I consider AI integration a time-saving solution in lesson planning and delivery.	4.08	0.80	A	1
5. I am convinced that AI will make me a more effective and efficient teacher in the mathematics classroom.	4.00	0.85	A	4.5
6. I anticipate that AI integration will lead to greater student engagement and motivation.	4.00	0.94	A	4.5

7.	I see AI as a means to provide more individualized support to students.	3.84	0.99	A	9
8.	I expect that AI will enhance the learning experience for both students and teachers.	3.95	0.94	A	8
9.	I envision AI as a tool for addressing diverse learning needs in the classroom.	3.97	0.90	A	7
Grand Mean		3.98	0.88	A	
Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation		
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	The level of perceived usefulness is very high		
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	The level of perceived usefulness is high		
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	The level of perceived usefulness is average		
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	The level of perceived usefulness is low		
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	The level of perceived usefulness is very low		

Table 9

Perceived Challenges of Senior High School Mathematics Teachers on Integrating AI in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

Indicators		Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
1.	I lack training on how to effectively use AI teaching tools.	3.86	0.95	A	3
2.	I don't have enough time to learn and implement new AI technologies.	3.46	0.93	A	8
3.	I have concerns about data privacy and ethical issues related to AI.	3.76	0.80	A	5
4.	I lack technical support for troubleshooting problems with AI tools.	3.68	0.94	A	6
5.	Students may resist or be skeptical about using AI technologies.	3.41	1.04	MA	9
6.	AI tools may not align well with my curriculum and learning objectives.	3.35	1.03	MA	10
7.	It is difficult to customize or optimize AI tools for my students' needs.	3.51	1.02	A	7
8.	Unreliable internet connectivity or lack of devices limits my ability to adopt AI.	3.81	1.00	A	4
9.	High costs are associated with purchasing or licensing quality AI solutions.	4.14	0.92	A	1
10.	AI tools feel impersonal and lack human interaction.	3.89	0.91	A	2
Grand Mean		3.69	0.96	A	
Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation		
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	The level of perceived challenges is very high		
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	The level of perceived challenges is high		
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	The level of perceived challenges is average		
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	The level of perceived challenges is low		
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	The level of perceived challenges is very low		

IV. Readiness of Senior High School Mathematics Teacher in AI Integration

Table 10 shows the descriptive interpretation of teachers' readiness to use AI tools for teaching. This variable is presumed to be one of the factors that affect the perception and readiness of the respondents in AI integration. Table 10 displays respondents' self-reported readiness to integrate AI tools in teaching math. The mean scores ranged from 2.97 to 4.14, indicating overall moderate to high readiness levels.

Table 10

Level of Readiness of Senior High School Mathematics Teachers to Use AI Tools for Teaching in Selected Public and Private Secondary School

Indicators	Mean	SD	V.I	Rank
1. I feel prepared to start using AI technologies in my teaching.	3.62	0.86	A	8
2. I have the knowledge needed to use AI tools effectively for instruction.	3.51	0.80	A	11
3. I am willing to invest time in learning how to use new AI teaching tools.	4.00	0.85	A	6
4. I feel confident in my ability to troubleshoot issues with AI technologies.	3.54	0.90	A	9.5
5. I have access to the resources I would need to implement AI tools in my classroom.	3.54	0.93	A	9.5
6. My school provides sufficient training for using instructional AI technologies.	2.97	1.12	MA	14
7. I stay up-to-date on new AI innovations that could enhance my teaching.	3.35	0.89	MA	12
8. I am excited by the potential for AI to improve student outcomes and my effectiveness.	4.08	0.86	A	4
9. I feel ready to integrate AI into my daily teaching practice.	3.70	0.88	A	7
10. I am open to adjusting my teaching methods to incorporate AI innovations.	4.11	0.81	A	2.5
11. I believe that integrating AI technologies would enhance the overall effectiveness of my teaching.	4.11	0.81	A	2.5
12. I am willing to collaborate with colleagues to share insights and strategies for integrating AI into teaching practices.	4.14	0.95	A	1
13. My educational institution provides the necessary technological infrastructure to support the integration of AI tools.	3.32	1.03	MA	13
14. I am committed to ongoing professional development to enhance my knowledge and skills related to AI in education.	4.05	0.88	A	5
Grand Mean	3.72	0.90	A	

Legend: Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	The level of readiness is very high
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	The level of readiness is high
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	The level of readiness is average
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	The level of readiness is low
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	The level of readiness is very low

V. Significant Relationship between Variables

Table 11.1 to 15 shows inferential statistics showing the significant relationship between profile and teachers' level of familiarity, teachers' perspective, and level of readiness. Also, the significant relationship between the two variables familiarity and readiness and teachers' perspective and readiness at 0.05 significant level.

Table 11.1

Test of Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Level of Familiarity with AI tools

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	-0.328	Low relationship	0.048	Reject H ₀
Age	-0.172	Negligible relationship	0.309	Accept H ₀
Educational Attainment	-0.082	Negligible relationship	0.629	Accept H ₀

Length of Service	-0.037	Negligible relationship	0.826	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	0.461	Moderate relationship	0.004	Reject H ₀

Table 11.2

Test of Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Level of Familiarity with common features of AI tools

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	-0.360	Low relationship	0.029	Reject H ₀
Age	-0.383	Low relationship	0.019	Reject H ₀
Educational Attainment	-0.261	Low relationship	0.118	Accept H ₀
Length of Service	-0.282	Low relationship	0.091	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	0.428	Moderate relationship	0.008	Reject H ₀

Table 11.3

Test of Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Level of Familiarity in integrating AI tools in teaching

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	-0.235	Low relationship	0.162	Accept H ₀
Age	-0.465	Moderate relationship	0.004	Reject H ₀
Educational Attainment	-0.297	Low relationship	0.074	Accept H ₀
Length of Service	-0.266	Low relationship	0.111	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	0.382	Low relationship	0.020	Reject H ₀

Table 12.1

Test of Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Perspective in Ease of Use

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	0.309	Low relationship	0.062	Accept H ₀
Age	0.191	Negligible relationship	0.258	Accept H ₀
Educational Attainment	-0.076	Negligible relationship	0.656	Accept H ₀
Length of Service	0.090	Negligible relationship	0.596	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	-0.141	Negligible relationship	0.405	Accept H ₀

Table 12.2

Test of Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Perspective in Usefulness

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	0.223	Low relationship	0.185	Accept H ₀
Age	0.079	Negligible relationship	0.643	Accept H ₀
Educational Attainment	-0.062	Negligible relationship	0.714	Accept H ₀
Length of Service	0.062	Negligible relationship	0.714	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	-0.029	Negligible relationship	0.863	Accept H ₀

Table 12.3*Test of Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Perspective in Challenges of AI Integration*

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	-0.013	Negligible relationship	0.939	Accept H ₀
Age	0.133	Negligible relationship	0.431	Accept H ₀
Educational Attainment	0.033	Negligible relationship	0.847	Accept H ₀
Length of Service	0.060	Negligible relationship	0.726	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	-0.035	Negligible relationship	0.837	Accept H ₀

Table 13*Test of Relationship between Profile and Readiness of Respondents*

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Sex	0.348	Low relationship	0.035	Reject H ₀
Age	0.154	Negligible relationship	0.364	Accept H ₀
Educational Attainment	0.330	Low relationship	0.848	Accept H ₀
Length of Service	0.087	Negligible relationship	0.607	Accept H ₀
Technological competence	-0.061	Negligible relationship	0.720	Accept H ₀

Table 14*Test of Relationship between Level of Familiarity and Readiness of Respondents*

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Familiarity with AI tools	-0.380	Low relationship	0.020	Reject H ₀
Familiarity with the features of AI	-0.362	Low relationship	0.028	Reject H ₀
Familiarity with integrating AI into teaching	-0.477	Moderate relationship	0.003	Reject H ₀

Table 15*Test of Relationship between Perspective and Readiness of Respondents*

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Perspective in ease of use	0.727	High relationship	<0.000	Reject H ₀
Perspective in usefulness	0.656	Moderate relationship	<0.000	Reject H ₀
Perspective on challenges of AI integration	0.641	Moderate relationship	<0.000	Reject H ₀

DISCUSSION

I. Demographic Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

Table 1 The table summarizes the demographics, including gender, age, education, and tenure. It shows the distribution and frequency of the respondents across these categories, with a predominance of males, those aged 26-35, those with a Bachelor's degree, and those with 6-10 years of experience. The sample appears skewed toward more junior roles based on the tenure data. The total frequency and percentages are equal to 100, indicating full coverage of all respondents in the sample.

Table 2 The respondents positively evaluated their technical abilities across most skill areas ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.76$), aligning with Chou et al. (2022), who found that professional development can significantly increase teachers' perceived ability and competence in utilizing AI technologies in the classroom. This supports the emphasis on providing training to equip teachers with the skills needed to leverage evolving AI tools for enhancing math instruction (Kohler, 2023)

Table 3 The findings reveal that math teachers use AI tools sparingly, with some technologies like Photomath, Mathway, Desmos, and Quizizz being used occasionally. This limited use highlights barriers to AI adoption in education, such as inadequate professional development and resource constraints, which require institutional interventions. Despite the limited current use, there is potential to increase AI tool adoption by providing technical training for educators and creating supportive environments for them to share their thoughts and concerns. Addressing these challenges through professional development and resource investment can enable math teachers to more extensively integrate AI tools into their teaching practices.

II. Familiarity of Teachers with Various AI tools

Table 4 The findings show that respondents were most familiar with specific math problem solvers like PhotoMath, Mathway, ChatGPT, Geogebra, Desmos, Quizizz, and Kahoot, while other AI technologies were only slightly familiar. The higher familiarity with problem solvers and graphing calculators reflects their frequent use and applicability in math classrooms. However, the lower familiarity with other AI technologies suggests a gap in exposure and training. Addressing this gap requires equipping teachers with the skills to leverage evolving AI tools to enhance math instruction through further learning and professional development (Kohler, 2023).

Table 5 The findings indicate that respondents were most familiar with assessment tools, followed by math problem solvers, tutors, and graphing tools, while computer algebra and programming tools were less familiar. This reveals existing knowledge in some areas and potential gaps in others regarding AI capabilities for math education. The higher familiarity with tools like Photomath, Wolfram Alpha, and Desmos aligns with their frequent use in classrooms. However, the lower familiarity with computer algebra systems and programming tools highlights a need for more comprehensive training on AI applications. More work is needed to equip teachers with the skills to leverage evolving AI tools to enhance math instruction (Kohler, 2023).

Table 6 The findings suggest that additional training on AI's instructional skills, particularly its advanced adaptive features, could enhance teachers' knowledge, indicating a need for equipping teachers with the skills to leverage evolving AI tools for math instruction (Kohler, 2023). The results highlight current understanding levels and opportunities for gaining skills in effectively using AI tools to enhance math teaching. This aligns with Kim & Kim (2022), who emphasize that providing technical training for

teachers is crucial for enhancing their technological competence when integrating AI into math classrooms.

III. Teachers Perspective in Using AI tools in teaching Mathematics

Table 7 The findings suggest that teachers' adoption of AI tools may be influenced by their perception of ease of use. If teachers find AI tools uncomplicated and straightforward for math instruction, it reduces barriers and increases openness to integrating the technology. Viewing ease of use as a benefit can facilitate AI adoption by making the integration process seem more achievable for math teachers.

Table 8 The finding that the perception of AI tools as applicable could motivate adoption among teachers is consistent with the concept that teachers' attitudes toward AI utilization were influenced by their understanding of how AI can be incorporated into the curriculum (Kim & Kim, 2022). When teachers perceive AI tools as valuable and easy to use for boosting math instruction, they are more likely to adopt and integrate these technologies into their teaching practices. The study suggests that demonstrating real AI applications and their instructional benefits may increase teacher adoption by reinforcing their impressions of AI's utility in Math education.

Table 9 The findings show that the top perceived challenges to AI adoption in education are high solution costs, insufficient training, and the impersonal feel or lack of human touch from AI tools. These align with the common barriers identified in the literature. The high costs of AI tools and applications can be a significant obstacle for schools and universities. Additionally, a lack of technical skills and knowledge among educators is widely recognized as a major barrier, highlighting the necessity for substantial professional development and training programs. Furthermore, the lack of personal connection and emotional intelligence in AI raises concerns about its ability to understand and empathize with students' emotional needs. By identifying these key challenges around cost, training, and the human touch, the findings provide valuable insights that can guide efforts to optimize AI integration, such as investing in resources, providing comprehensive training, and exploring ways to humanize AI interactions.

IV. Readiness of Senior High School Mathematics Teacher in AI Integration

Table 10 The findings show a grand mean of 3.72, demonstrating overall agreement with statements about readiness to employ AI tools in teaching. This indicates that respondents typically possess the knowledge required to utilize AI tools in their instruction practices. The study suggests that focused training interventions can effectively improve teacher readiness for AI integration. Furthermore, the opportunity to address lower-ranking readiness areas through knowledge sharing aligns with recommendations that continued peer collaboration helps maintain and enhance technical skills over time. While some development needs exist based on the mean score, the overall agreement on readiness mapping indicates that teachers can gain the necessary skills and confidence to effectively integrate AI tools into their math instruction practices with sufficient training and collaborative support mechanisms. The findings suggest a solid foundational

readiness that can be further strengthened through professional development efforts, including training programs and opportunities for peer collaboration and knowledge sharing.

V. Significant Relationship between Variables

Table 11. 1 The findings suggest that lack of technical skills and knowledge is the top barrier to adopting AI, implying that higher competence enables greater familiarity with the tools. Sex differences do not show a significant relationship with familiarity with AI tools, highlighting a research gap. Age, education, and tenure factors also do not have significant relationships, indicating that individual demographics play a lesser role than skills like technological competence in determining AI tool familiarity. Providing technical training for educators is essential to increase competence, which is a key factor linked to familiarity.

Table 11. 2 The findings indicate that sex does not significantly influence familiarity with AI features, aligning with previous studies showing that attitudes towards AI tools are not impacted by respondents' sex. However, age negatively correlates with technology readiness, highlighting the importance of technological competence. Lack of technical competence is reported as the primary barrier to adopting AI-enabled educational software, emphasizing the need for robust professional development to build teachers' AI proficiency. While educational attainment and length of service were not directly addressed, there is a suggestion to incorporate AI literacy into teacher education programs and target training on AI features for groups less familiar, such as older or less tech-savvy teachers.

Table 11.3 The findings indicate significant relationships between age and technological competence with familiarity in integrating AI tools, whereas sex, education, and tenure show no significant relationships. Age negatively correlates with technology readiness, suggesting younger teachers may be more familiar with AI integration. The importance of technological competence is underscored, as lack of it is reported as the primary barrier to adopting AI-enabled educational software, and robust professional development can enhance teachers' AI proficiency. Although education and tenure were not directly addressed, there is a suggestion to incorporate AI literacy into teacher education programs and focus professional development on building AI integration competencies for older and less technologically proficient teachers.

Table 12.1 The findings indicate that none of the profile characteristics such as sex, age, education, tenure, or technological competence have significant relationships with respondents' perspectives on the ease of use of AI tools in mathematics classrooms. This suggests that perceptions of AI usability are consistent across teachers' demographics regardless of these factors. While previous research has shown no significant impact of sex on attitudes toward AI tools, contrasting evidence suggests a positive link between teachers' technological competence in AI integration and their perceptions of AI's usefulness and ease of use, contradicting the finding for technological competence in this study. Currently, no previous literature reviews support the relationship between age, education, and tenure, which is also noted as a research gap in the study.

Table 12. 2 The findings indicate that none of the profile characteristics have significant relationships with respondents' perspectives on the ease of use of AI tools. This suggests that perceptions of AI usability are consistent across teachers' demographics regardless of gender, age, educational background, years of experience, or level of technological competence. While a related study supports the finding for gender, noting no significant impact on attitudes toward AI tools, it also found a positive link between teachers' technological competence in AI integration and their perceptions of AI's usefulness and ease of use, contradicting the findings regarding technological competence in this study. There is currently no previous evidence or literature reviews to support relationships with age, education, and tenure specifically, which is also noted as a research gap.

Table 12. 3 The findings indicate that none of the profile variables, including sex, age, education level, experience, and technological competence, have significant relationships with perspectives on AI integration challenges. This suggests that views of obstacles or challenges are consistent across teacher demographics in this sample. While a related study supports the finding for gender, noting no significant impact on attitudes toward AI tools, it also found a positive link between teachers' technological competence in AI integration and their perceptions of AI's usefulness and ease of use, contradicting the findings regarding technological competence in this study. Meanwhile, opposing findings suggest that age negatively correlates with technology readiness, implying that younger teachers may be more familiar with AI integration. There is currently no previous evidence or literature reviews to support relationships between education and tenure, respectively, which is noted as one of the research's gaps.

Table 13 The findings reveal that only sex has a significant relationship with respondents' readiness to use AI tools, while age, education level, experience, and technological competence do not. This contrasts with previous research suggesting no significant impact of sex on attitudes toward AI tools and a positive link between technological competence and perceptions of AI's usefulness and ease of use. Additionally, the lack of significant relationships with age contradicts findings suggesting a negative correlation between age and technology readiness. The importance of technological competence is highlighted, despite its lack of influence on readiness in this study, as robust professional development can build teachers' AI proficiency. There is currently no evidence supporting relationships between educational attainment, length of service, and readiness, marking a research gap.

Table 14 The findings indicate a contrasting relationship between familiarity with AI and readiness to use it, with less familiar teachers being more ready to use AI while more familiar ones are less ready. One potential explanation for this is the familiarity breeds caution effect, where increased familiarity with AI technologies leads to a better understanding of their complexities and potential risks, thus fostering a more cautious approach to adoption. This aligns with prior research suggesting that teachers' prior experiences and understanding of AI influence their attitudes toward it (Kim & Kim, 2022). While initially open to new technologies like AI, increased familiarity may uncover challenges such as the need for technical skills and concerns about its impact on teacher roles (Celik et al., 2022). The findings underscore the importance of ongoing support,

training, and resources to address these issues, as recommended in the literature. The openness of less familiar teachers highlights the value of proactively building AI skills through teacher education programs.

Table 15 The findings reveal moderate to high positive correlations between the perspective variables, indicating that teachers' readiness to adopt AI tools increases when they view AI more favorably in terms of ease of use, usefulness, and perceived challenges as manageable. This aligns with previous research, where concerns about impacts on teacher autonomy and roles underscore the importance of seeing challenges as something that can be overcome to facilitate readiness (Celik et al., 2022). These perspectives highlight key factors influencing technology adoption, such as training to build competence and addressing external barriers like lack of resources (Seo et al., 2021). Overall, the findings are consistent with evidence showing more positive views on AI's utility, feasibility, and ability to overcome obstacles, correlating with increased openness among teachers.

VI. Proposed Intervention Program

Based on the consolidated results of the study, a comprehensive “One-year Intervention program” was crafted. This proposed intervention program titled “Enhancing AI Literacy and Integration in Education” focused on the areas needing improvement, such as familiarity and usage of specific AI tools, knowledge of integrating advanced AI capabilities, training and resources, technical skills and support, cost and infrastructure, and ethical and privacy concerns around AI usage.

In crafting the research development plan, the researcher utilized an adapted, modified format from the Department of Education. This Program Intervention Matrix outlines a comprehensive plan to equip senior high school Mathematics teachers with the necessary skills, knowledge, and support to effectively integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools into their teaching practices. The matrix is structured into three levels (Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced), each addressing specific objectives and components.

Conclusions

The study provided insights into senior high school mathematics teachers' perspectives, familiarity, and readiness in integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their classrooms. The findings revealed a generally positive outlook, with teachers recognizing AI's potential benefits in enhancing teaching effectiveness, personalizing learning experiences, and improving student outcomes.

However, the respondents' familiarity with AI tools and their integration varied, with moderate familiarity in some areas and a need for improvement in others, such as computer algebra systems and programming computation tools. Their familiarity with integrating AI into teaching practices was moderate, indicating a need for further training and professional development.

The study highlighted challenges in adopting AI technologies, including high costs, concerns about the impersonal nature of AI tools, the need for adequate training, internet connectivity issues, technical support, and aligning AI with the curriculum and objectives.

Despite these challenges, the respondents demonstrated a strong willingness to adapt their teaching methods, collaborate with colleagues, and engage in professional development to integrate AI effectively. Their readiness levels were positively influenced by their perceptions of the ease of use and usefulness of AI tools and their understanding of the challenges involved.

Technological competence, age, and sex were significant factors in predicting familiarity with AI tools and their features, while demographic variables such as educational attainment and length of service showed negligible relationships with AI familiarity, perspectives, and readiness.

A proposed intervention program was considered to provide comprehensive training for teachers on utilizing AI tools effectively, guidance on integrating AI into lesson plans and assessments, strategies for addressing ethical considerations and data privacy issues, facilitating collaboration among teachers, offering technical support, and exploring cost-effective solutions for acquiring AI technologies.

Overall, the findings underscored the need for comprehensive training programs, adequate technological infrastructure, and support systems to facilitate the successful integration of AI into mathematics classrooms. By addressing these challenges and leveraging the positive attitudes and willingness of teachers, the potential of AI to enhance teaching and learning experiences can be fully realized.

Recommendations

1. Educational institutions should invest in comprehensive professional development programs that enhance mathematics teachers' familiarity with AI tools, their features, and their integration into instruction. These programs should provide hands-on training and workshops, in collaboration with educational technology experts and AI solution providers.
2. A solid technological infrastructure and support system are essential for effective use of AI tools in math instruction. This includes investing in reliable internet connectivity, up-to-date devices, and a dedicated technical support team. School administrators should also explore cost-effective solutions and partnerships to acquire quality AI solutions at reasonable prices.
3. To maximize the benefits of AI in math education, AI tools must align with the curriculum standards and objectives. Policymakers, curriculum developers, and subject matter experts should collaborate to ensure seamless integration of AI tools into lesson plans, assessments, and instructional strategies, fostering a collaborative approach among teachers.

4. Clear policies, teacher training, and open dialogue are necessary to address ethical and privacy concerns associated with the use of AI tools in math education. Educational institutions should develop guidelines, provide training on addressing potential risks, and promote balanced discussions among stakeholders.
5. Fostering collaboration and community building among math teachers is crucial for effective AI integration. Educational institutions should establish professional learning communities, encourage participation in online forums and conferences, and foster partnerships with AI technology companies to facilitate knowledge sharing and resource exchange.
6. Regular evaluations and feedback mechanisms should be implemented to assess the effectiveness of AI integration in mathematics classrooms. Data should be gathered on student learning outcomes, engagement, and motivation to make data-driven decisions for improvement, and teachers should be encouraged to provide feedback and suggestions.
7. Future researchers should continue to investigate the evolving landscape of AI in education, exploring new tools, strategies, and best practices and contributing to the growing body of knowledge in this field.
8. Propose program Intervention for consideration of school heads. To equip teacher to properly Integrate AI inside the classroom.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research, the researcher adhered to the highest ethical standards to ensure the integrity of the study and the protection of the participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, benefits, and their rights. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained by anonymizing data and securely storing all information. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions. The research design prioritized minimizing any potential harm, and transparency was maintained throughout the process.

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